

ON EMERGING CIVIC SPACES' ROLE IN INNOVATIVE LOCAL SOCIO-ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT, RIACE AS A CASE

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Abstract: There seems to be a political inaction and stagnating local socio-economic development (LSED) in rural and peri-urban areas of Calabria Region in southern Italy. In response, this paper, based on literature review and case study, seeks to cast light on an innovative LSED pattern driven by emerging civic spaces. To this end, this paper carries out a case study of Riace so as to explore the dynamics, forms and socio-economic impacts of emerging civic spaces in relation to innovative LSED. By analysing the quantitative data collected from Istat and qualitative data collected from field studies and interviews of key stakeholders, it looks into the emerging multicultural civic spaces in Riace, focusing on their impacts on socio-economic innovation. Finally, based on the case study, the paper points out the viability of adopting a place-based and community-driven approach to LSED. It concludes that civic spaces, formed through the empowerment of local population and community collaboration, stimulates socio-cultural and economic innovation, which serves as a driver of LSED.

Keywords: Civic Spaces, Community Collaboration, Innovation, Local Socio-Economic Development (LSED), Territory.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Literature Review

Civic spaces, where “civic entrepreneurship” occurs (Goldsmith *et al.*, 2010), are perceived mainly in two ways within the academia. On the one hand, civic spaces are physical spaces with an embedded value system. While they serve as physical sites for civil society to organise and function autonomously, they represent a value system composed of place-making ingredients, such as identity, meaning, memory, history and linkages with the rest of the world (Danieri & Douglass, 2008). Without these place-making ingredients, which are in essence social and cultural capital, a place tends to lose its vitality due to community decohesion. On the other hand, civic spaces are also popularly seen as a social construct with a political economic implication. Therefore, they are inclusive social spaces with a high degree of autonomy from the state and corporate economy (Danieri, 2003). According to Abrahamson (2008: 3), they describe “the social processes of defining membership and exclusion, rules of interaction, and the desired image of the civic process”. Indeed, inclusiveness of civic spaces is vital to the well-being of society, in that it contributes to “the social and political life of cities through public participation in place-making and governance” (Douglass & Danieri, 2008: 1).

In fact, a participatory planning process accompanied by a decentralisation process is commonly acknowledged as indispensable for the formation and functionality of civic spaces (Danieri, 2003; Balassiano, 2011). Meanwhile, civic spaces are important contexts to have a precise understanding of participation and the underlying processes of empowerment (Huq,

2013). In terms of local development, participatory approach is believed to contribute to sustainable development (Strzelecka, 2011). As contributing factors for the formation of a participatory community, community empowerment and institutional autonomy are principal preconditions for alternative approaches to local development—decentralised sectoral, local government, and community support approaches (Serrano *et al.*, 2010). To guarantee a quality community empowerment, Aswad proposes a combined approach that incorporates procedural justice in planning development and social learning in its implementation (Kolo, 2002; Aswad, 2013). The procedural justice implies a process of community involvement in policy making and implementation. In this process, social learning contributes to policy making and implementation by providing context-based evidence and building relationships among stakeholders (Cundill & Rodela, 2012). It is obvious that community involvement is impossible without community empowerment achieved with a participatory approach.

According to Daniere (2003), civic spaces emerge as a response to globally-linked economic growth and access to information. However, the existing literature does not overtly touch upon the relationship between civic spaces and LSED. Besides, their socio-cultural and economic impacts are barely discussed. As for Riace in Calabria Region in southern Italy, emerging civic spaces are more of a response to unfavourable external political-economic environment and resulting endogenous place-based local socio-economic development (LSED) led by the civil society. Just as Abrahamson (2008: 3) remarks, civic spaces represent “the role of the citizen in the operation and oversight of the government”. Taking into account the realities in Calabria Region and the limitation of the existing literature, the authors pose such questions as:

- 1) How do emerging civic spaces contribute to innovative LSED?;
- 2) Do civic spaces also represent the role of the non-citizens, namely, immigrants?

The following sections dedicated to the case study of Riace will help answer these two questions.

1.2. Objective and Significance

As mentioned earlier, currently academic discussions on civic spaces seldom deal with the socio-economic impacts of civic spaces, especially in a multicultural community. That is to say, the role of civic spaces in LSED is not explicitly discussed. Therefore, this paper is aimed to explore the dynamics, forms and socio-economic impacts of civic spaces in relation to innovative LSED.

It is desirable that this research invite more future discussions on the socio-economic impacts of civic spaces in relation to local development. In addition, it is also hoped that policy-makers, will be more willing to adopt an innovative approach to local development which is driven by emerging civic spaces.

1.3. Methodology

This research carried out a case study of Riace so as to explore the dynamics, forms and socio-economic impacts of emerging civic spaces in relation to innovative LSED. For this purpose, it adopted both quantitative and qualitative methods. It first of all carried out a literature review to build up the theoretical structure of the entire research. Then

quantitatively speaking, it collected secondary baseline data of 1991, 2001 and 2011 from Istat, especially those on demography and economic performance, such as population, rate of foreign residents, old age index, young household with children rate, potential vacancy of buildings and unemployment rate of Riace and Roghudi (the latter was chosen as a contrast). By comparing these quantitative data, the regenerative effect of emerging civic spaces is indicated, in terms of community structure, population rejuvenation, reuse of abandoned buildings, job creation, etc. Qualitatively speaking, it undertook field studies¹ so as to gather various visual observations with regard to the forms, functions, mechanism, etc. of civic spaces that appear in Riace. Besides, it administered semi-structured interviews with key stakeholders, especially the Mayor of Riace.

2. CIVIC SPACES AND SOCIO-ECONOMIC INNOVATION IN RIACE

2.1. Background

Calabria Region boasts many minor historic centres (MHCs) of Greek origins, which are well-known for their strong territorial identity and rich cultural and landscape heritage. Often located in mountainous inner areas, they are isolated from the urban basin, which partly explains their delicate socio-economic conditions. Over the past three decades, these MHCs have gone through a continuous socio-economic decline due to aging population accompanied by outbound migration and low birth rate, changes in productive patterns, natural disasters, and demographic concentration in new settlements of the towns along the coast. While these new settlements keep the name of the towns, they are often differentiated from the latter with the word “marina”, since they are coastal. Riace (the new settlement of the town is called Riace Marina), the focus of this paper, is one of these MHCs.

The name of Riace probably came from the Greek-Byzantine “*Ryaki*” which means small brook. Since the refugee crisis in Europe, Riace has gradually earned an international fame because of its innovative approach to dealing with refugees. From 2004 until today, it has been the centre of immigration policy. In 2016 only, more than 800 immigrants were hosted by the local community, which helped revitalise the town itself.

As mentioned above, Riace, like many other MHCs, has suffered from aging population and depopulation since the 1980s. To better illustrate its “demographic crisis”, Roghudi², having similar conditions, was chosen as a contrast. The geographic location of Riace and Roghudi is shown in the map below (see Map 1). The table below (see Table 1) shows their population, old age index, young household with children rate and potential vacancy of buildings in 1991, 2001 and 2011. While there is a constantly decreasing population and young household with children rate as well as a constantly increasing old age index in Roghudi, Riace saw an increasing population and young household with children rate as well as a decreasing old age index in 2011, which implies an increase of immigrants. This increase of immigrants is also confirmed by a significant decrease in potential vacancy of buildings in both towns.

¹ The co-author Antonio Errigo carried out all the field investigations and interviews.

² As an ancient settlement, Roghudi owes its name perhaps to the ancient Greek “*Rochùdios*”. The Old Roghudi (Roghudi Vecchio) enjoys a breath-taking landscape: it is located on the top of a hill about 500 meters above sea level which stands right in the middle of the seasonal river Amendolea. Following the floods in the early 1970s, the old town was abandoned and all of its inhabitants were relocated to the newly constructed town called New Roghudi (Roghudi Nuovo, hereinafter referred to as Roghudi) in Melito Porto Salvo, very close to the Ionian coast.

It is worth noting that in Riace, inverse changes have been happening since 2001. For example, its old age index increased from 1991 to 2001 and decreased from 2001 to 2011. Meanwhile, its population and young household with children rate decreased from 1991 to 2001 and increased from 2001 to 2011. Since civic spaces have started to emerge in Riace since 1999, which is to be discussed in detail in the following section, the year 2001 was considered as a baseline year to catch the trend before and after with the emergence of civic spaces. It therefore can be concluded that emerging civic spaces have helped rejuvenate the population of Riace and regenerate the town.

The emerging civic spaces in Riace are mainly represented and fostered by autonomous NGOs (under the coordination of the institutional leadership, namely, the mayor) and collaboration between the host community and the guest community. In the following sections, the dynamics, forms and socio-economic impacts of emerging civic spaces in relation to innovative LSED are discussed in detail.

Map 1: Geographic location of Roghudi and Riace³

Source: Google Map (2017).

Processed by A. Errigo.

Table 1⁴: Population, old age index, young household with children rate and potential vacancy of buildings in 1991, 2001 and 2011 in Roghudi and Riace

Source: Istat, 8000 Census. Retrieved from <http://ottomilacensus.istat.it/provincia/080/>, accessed on 26/05/2017.

Town	Indicators	1991	2001	2011
Roghudi	Population	1,530	1,365	1,172
Riace		1,694	1,605	1,793
Roghudi	Old age index	75.4	118.5	143.4
Riace		103.5	117.2	116.8
Roghudi	Young household with children rate	20.1	14.5	8.1
Riace		18.1	11.3	13.5
Roghudi	Potential vacancy of buildings	NA	23.3	18.3
Riace		NA	11.7	8.2

³ The boundary in thick white line shows the metropolitan city of Reggio Calabria. The inner white boundaries are the administrative territorial divisions (i comuni).

⁴ Notes: Old age index: percentage of population aged 65 years old and over and that aged 0-14 years old; Unemployment rate: Percentage of residents seeking job in relation to active population (employed and job-hunting); Incidence of foreign residents: incidence of foreign residents per 1,000 Italian residents; Potential vacancy of buildings: percentage of unused buildings on total buildings.

2.2. Multicultural Community Building and Social Inclusion

Both Roghudi and Riace are hosting immigrants to rejuvenate their population and regenerate their urban fabrics, but it is Riace that has a longer tradition of being open to immigrants that dates back to the 1990s. As the table below (see Table 2) shows, the number of foreign residents is rocketing up in both towns, especially in Roghudi.

The drastically increasing number of immigrants, just like a double-edged sword, proves to be both an opportunity and a risk. Immigrants mean not only more labour force and cultural diversity, but also possible tension and even conflict between the host community and the guest community. When referring to the new patterns of migration to Pacific Asia's metropolitan regions, Douglass (2003) maintains that whether the accompanying cultural diversity can be accomplished in a socially just, inclusive manner is among the most important issues of this century. Often times, a so-called "crisis of inclusion" happens when there is a troubled access to public and civic spaces (Danieri, 2003). Indeed, how to foster a multicultural community that is socially and economically inclusive to all community members is undoubtedly an important but challenging task for Riace.

Table 2: Rate of foreign residents in Roghudi and Riace

Source: Istat, 8000 Census. Retrieved from <http://ottomilacensus.istat.it/provincia/080/>, accessed on 26/05/2017.

Town	Indicators	1991	2001	2011
Roghudi	Rate of foreign residents	3.9	58.6	120.3
Riace		1.8	12.5	56.9

In Riace, grass-roots NGOs (under the coordination of the institutional leadership, namely, the mayor), such as associations and cooperatives, have played a significant role in promoting integration and inclusion of the immigrants, while building up the towns' social capital. NGOs often have a significant role to play in decentralisation (Balassiano, 2011). This can be evidenced by the autonomy of local associations in Riace in planning and implementing cultural initiatives aimed at the integration of immigrants. In 1999, the association *Città Futura* (Future City), the first of its type, was founded in Riace, echoed successively by four other associations A Sud di Lampedusa, Girasole, Real Riace and Riace Accoglie. These associations have collaboratively planned and carried out a series of welcome projects for immigrants, which has finally become a national and international prototype, the "Riace Model". In the following section, this paper will have a close look at the work of the leading non-profit organisation *Città Futura*, which is directed by the Mayor of Riace, Domenico Lucano⁵.

Città Futura is aimed at promoting and managing the activities related to the integration of immigrants. It also serves as a research institution for ethnographic history and culture. Its major objectives are:

- facilitating the socio-economic integration of foreigners present in Riace;
- creating jobs for unemployed young people;
- improving the local economy;
- making sure that the history of Riace can continue to live by means of folklore, traditions and handicrafts.

⁵ Currently serving his third term as Mayor of Riace, Domenico Lucano was listed by *Fortune* as one of the world's greatest leaders in 2016.

Basically speaking, *Città Futura* is dedicated to promoting the integration of immigrants in four ways: housing provision, conscious urban design, amenities improvement and public spaces diversification. To begin with, *Città Futura* developed a project of hospitality called Global Village (*Villaggio Globale*). Through the project, now completed, more than 20 abandoned houses were reclaimed, generating a total of more than 100 beds. With this project, the organisation has successfully combined the need of social integration and urban regeneration. It is worth noting that the Global Village is a very innovative project, in that it is not only aimed at improving housing for immigrants, but also creating new jobs. A typical design based on mixed use, Global Village, besides housing, also established bars, taverns, shops, etc. Actually, the Global Village, through the reclamation of abandoned buildings, is probably the key to foster civic spaces according to the Mayor. The shops, which sell different kinds of handicrafts, have contributed to regenerate and revitalise the historic centre of Riace, stimulate the local economic activities and allow immigrants to learn local skills necessary for making a living.

Secondly, with conscious considerations of the need to promote social inclusion of immigrants in public spaces, *Città Futura* has helped design public signs (see Figure 1) and decorative structures (see Figures 2-3) that all convey the value of tolerance and cultural diversity.

Figure 1: Public board showing nationalities present in Riace
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Figure 2: "Welcome to Riace", signs of welcome on the gate of Riace
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Thirdly, to help deliver better public services, *Città Futura* promoted the provision of various public amenities, such as theatre (see Figure 4), where performances and citizen meetings take place, and oil mill with stone grinders for the production of extra virgin olive oil (see Figure 5).

Figure 3: Mural painting and “Global Village”, entrance arch to the shops
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Figure 4: Theatre of Riace
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In addition, to make sure that different ethnic groups can interact and socialise with each other, *Città Futura* has realised a series of projects focusing on public spaces. Some of the existing squares in the historic centre were rehabilitated with considerations of social integration promotion (see Figure 6).

Figure 5: Oil mill with stone grinders for the production of extra virgin olive oil
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Figure 6: A small square in the historic centre transformed into a stage decorated with multi-ethnic paintings
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2.3. Community Collaboration and Economic Inclusion

It is acknowledged that people’s capabilities to participate effectively in local development are determined not only by individual resource endowments, but also by social capital that provides the basis for collective action (Serrano *et al.*, 2010). As mentioned above, in Riace local NGOs have helped build up the community’s social capital by promoting integration and socio-cultural inclusion. This serves as a starting point for the host community and guest community to collaborate. In so doing, besides socio-cultural inclusion, economic inclusion is also achieved, since new jobs, especially jobs for immigrants, are created. As the table below (see Table 3) demonstrates, there was a constant decrease in unemployment rate in Roghudi. In contrast, Riace saw an increase in unemployment rate in 2011, which may be explained by the economic crisis across Europe.

Table 3: Unemployment rate in Roghudi and Riace

Source: Istat, 8000 Census. Retrieved from <http://ottomilacensus.istat.it/provincia/080/>, accessed on 26/05/2017.

Town	Indicators	1991	2001	2011
Roghudi	Unemployment rate	44.5	15.3	7.4
Riace		39.4	19.8	22.9

Community collaboration is deemed as a rural restructuring strategy (Baker, 1993). According to interviews with key stakeholders, Riace has freed itself from an over-dependency on traditional agricultural economy and moved towards new economic sectors. Tourism is a good example. By adding value to the Heritage, both material and immaterial, the host community and guest community collaborate to help promote tourism development. In Riace, for example, various artistic laboratories were established where immigrants can work as apprentices to learn handicrafts (see Figure 7), just to name a few, laboratories of glassware, embroidery, weaving (with traditional wooden looms), jam, etc. The handicrafts normally bear strong territorial identity, and they are popular commodities on the tourism market (see Figure 8). Community collaboration of this kind has not only added value to local Heritage and promoted the territorial identity, but also generated income for both the host community and guest community. Needless to say, this has contributed to local economic development.

Apart from artistic laboratories, the host community and the guest community collaborate, under the guidance of *Città Futura*, to revitalise agricultural production by reclaiming abandoned farming lands. A good example is the “Didactic Farm” (see Figure 9) dedicated to immigrants. This “Didactic Farm” allows immigrants to take advantage of the tools and facilities needed for agricultural work. For examples, they are instructed how to raise domestic animals in the small buildings on the farm (as is shown on the picture below).

Figure 8: Boutique selling local handicrafts while promoting fair trade concept
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Figure 7: Immigrant weaving in a laboratory
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Figure 9: Panoramic view on the “Didactic Farm”
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3. CONCLUSIONS

As the literature available demonstrates, currently academic discussions on civic spaces seldom deal with the socio-economic impacts of civic spaces, especially in a multicultural community. This research found that the emerging civic spaces in Riace are mainly represented and fostered by autonomous NGOs (under the coordination of the institutional leadership, namely, the mayor) and collaboration between the host community and the guest community. The emerging civic spaces do contribute to the integration of immigrants, and at the same time, the promotion of an innovative local socio-economic development. The socio-economic development in Riace proves to be innovative mainly because, firstly, local NGOs, *Città Futura* in particular, play a proactive role in promoting social and economic inclusion by building up a cohesive multicultural community. Housing provision for immigrants, conscious urban design, amenities improvement and public spaces diversification are crucial contributing factors leading to the success of Riace. Secondly, according to the needs of all community members, the historic centre of Riace has been regenerated and revitalised by mobilising the idle physical capital, namely, abandoned buildings. During the regeneration process, mixed use strategy, as the project Global Village shows, has been an effective, innovative tool for Riace to achieve both social integration and inclusive job creation. This strategy finally contributes to increasing community cohesion and local economic development through a value-adding of its Heritage (handicrafts for instance). Last but not the least, collaboration between the host community and the guest community has not only helped build up Riace’s social capital which is vital for its emerging civic spaces, but also contribute to its economic development, as the artistic laboratories and “Didactic Farm” demonstrate.

It is desirable that the findings of this research serve as an empirical reference for policy-making, especially for other communities in Calabria Region which have similar socio-economic challenges. Policy-makers would integrate into local development initiatives an innovative approach to local socio-economic development which is driven by emerging civic spaces. Besides, it is equally hoped that the role of civic spaces in innovative socio-economic development would be popularly acknowledged by both the academia and policy-makers, and more importantly, brought into play locally.

Due to space limitation, the research didn't discuss the role of the public sector in fostering the civic spaces, which is unarguably important in Riace. Future research may well fill this gap. In addition, it would be interesting to compare Riace to other minor historic centres which see emerging civic spaces as well. Finally, as Daniere (2003: 4) points out, that civic spaces "require rules of access and use if they are to function in an inclusive, fundamentally non-violent and civil manner", one more question for future research is, how should these civic spaces be properly managed and regulated?

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